

ANALYSIS AND TEST OF THIN INTEGRALLY STIFFENED FIBRE COMPOSITE PANELS

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ABSTRACT

Two thin-skinned, integrally stiffened, postbuckling composite panel designs have been analysed and tested in edgewise compression and shear. The postbuckling behaviour was predicted with geometric nonlinear finite element analysis using shell elements incorporating plane stress laminate theory. A test program is detailed in which the panel response was monitored using shadow moiré interferometry and electrical resistance strain gauges. The postbuckling designs are then compared with a conventional non-buckling composite sandwich design. Panels were also tested with barely visible impact damage and a significant reduction in static strength was demonstrated, although the postbuckling panels sustained much higher impact energies than the sandwich panels.

INTRODUCTION

Postbuckling fibre composite panels have been proposed as a means of achieving improvements in the structural efficiency of aerospace structures. They typically consist of thin skins stiffened with open or hat-section stiffeners and as well as reducing weight, have demonstrated superior durability and repairability when compared to conventional composite sandwich structures [1-3]. The behaviour of postbuckling stiffened composite panels has been investigated by many researchers [4-6] and the development of computational methods for postbuckling analysis has also been widely reported [7-10].

In this paper, two co-cured designs are evaluated: one with integral blade-stiffeners and the other with integral "I"-stiffeners. In both cases the stiffeners are run-out at the ends. The panels are designed for edgewise ultimate compression and shear loads of 200 N/mm and are typical of composite panels in secondary structural components such as control surfaces. The panels are designed to buckle at approximately one third of design ultimate load. Advanced finite element (FE) analysis techniques, incorporated in the general purpose code MSC/NASTRAN, are used to predict the postbuckling behaviour. The buckling mode shapes and corresponding strains at different load levels are calculated using shell elements incorporating plane stress laminate theory and geometric nonlinear methods. Laminate failure indices based on maximum ply strain criteria are used as a basis for the designs.

Edgewise compression and shear tests were carried out and the postbuckling behaviour was monitored using shadow moiré interferometry and electrical resistance strain gauges. A number of panels were tested with barely visible impact damage in order to assess the damage tolerance of the designs.

PANEL CONFIGURATIONS

The panel dimensions were determined by the size of the testing equipment which required a test section of 672 mm by 474 mm and a solid clamping region with overall dimensions of 914 mm by 594 mm. The panels were constructed with preimpregnated carbon-epoxy tape (Ciba Fibredux T300/914C) using conventional manufacturing and autoclave curing techniques. In each case the panels were designed with a solid laminate around the edge; this enabled the panels to be clamped into the test fixtures.

The sandwich panel consists of $[0/45/90/-45]$ skins and a 25 mm thick "Nomex" honeycomb (Hexcel HRH-10) core with a 20° taper at the edges. Additional 0° and $\pm 45^\circ$ plies reinforce the edge closeout, see Fig. 1. Eight panels were manufactured and the panel mass, including the solid edge region, varied between 1804 g and 2034 g with an average of 1910 g.

Figure 1. Sandwich panel configuration

The blade-stiffened panel design consists of five 25 mm high stiffeners which are run-out at an angle of 20° as shown in Fig. 2. The stiffeners are integral to the skin and consist of sixteen plies and the skin is a quasi-isotropic layup of eight plies. The edge clamping laminate is twenty plies at the ends and twelve plies at the sides. These additional plies are terminated in pairs near the stiffener run-outs. The stiffener laminate is symmetric and the skin alternates between symmetric and unsymmetric layups. Although asymmetry is undesirable due to coupling between membrane and bending deformations, this feature is unavoidable in an integral design in which $\pm 45^\circ$ plies are present in both the skin and the stiffeners. In this case the stability of the blade-stiffeners is considered more important than the skin which is allowed to buckle. Eight blade-stiffened panels were manufactured. The panel mass, including the solid edge region, varied between 1560 g and 1710 g with an average of 1646 g.

The "I"-stiffened panel is the same as the blade-stiffened panel except for the addition of a flange at the top of the stiffener web and the use of an alternative layup configuration. In this case it is considered that the stability of the top flange is more important than the web. The panel and flange layup is therefore symmetric and web is unsymmetric, see Fig. 3. In all other respects the "I"-stiffened panel design is the same as the blade-stiffened design. Four "I"-stiffened panels were manufactured using flexible tooling and conventional autoclave curing procedures. The panel mass, including the solid edge region, varied between 1748 g and 1899 g with an average of 1810 g.

Figure 2. Blade-stiffened panel ply configuration

Figure 3. Integral "I"-stiffener layup detail

ANALYSIS

An FE analysis of each panel design was carried out using MSC/NASTRAN version 67.5. In each case the composite laminates were modelled with 4-noded orthotropic shell elements (QUAD4) which incorporate classical laminate theory. The panel strengths were calculated using the maximum strain failure criteria and unaged material design allowables. The core in the sandwich panel was modelled using 8-noded orthotropic solid brick elements.

The deflections of the sandwich panel are "small" so it is considered that a linear static analysis is sufficient. For the blade- and "I"-stiffened panels the deflection of the thin structure can be "large", especially in postbuckling, so it is necessary to perform a geometric nonlinear analysis. A detailed discussion of the FE modelling of integral blade-stiffened panels is given by Scott [11] and Thomson et al [12].

Two load cases are considered. The first is an edgewise compression load of 200 N/mm on the short edges. The second is an edgewise shear load of 200 N/mm. Each load case corresponds to one of the test configurations, so that the FE modelling incorporated various features of the test setup. In the compression test the long edges are restrained from out-of-plane deformations. In the FE model these edges are therefore free to displace only in the direction of load. In the shear test the load is applied in a "picture frame" test fixture. This is modelled by loading the panel via stiff bar elements around the edges, see Ref. [12].

Table 1. Analysis results

	Sandwich	Blade-stiffened	"I"-stiffened
Compression - 200 N/mm			
End shortening (mm)	1.6	2.8	2.4
Max. out-of-plane displ. (mm)	0.8	14.0	11.0
Buckling load (N/mm)	-	85	110
Margin of safety	1.27	0.43	0.0
Shear - 200 N/mm			
Shear displacement (mm)	3.6	3.3	2.2
Buckling load (N/mm)	-	73	73
Margin of safety	0.35	-0.23	0.0

The results from the FE analysis are presented in Table 1. In compression, load is applied through the mid-plane of the skin so that overall bending results due to the offset of the neutral axis in the stiffened part of the panel. Note that these deflections for the postbuckling designs are significantly larger than those for the sandwich panel. The blade-stiffened panel design was actually completed using only a linear elastic analysis for the shear case and a geometric nonlinear analysis subsequently calculated the negative margin of safety. This highlights the fact that geometric nonlinear effects are highly significant. The large margin of safety for the sandwich panel in compression indicates that a thinner core could have been used. The design, however, was limited by the availability of core material. The predicted postbuckling behaviour of the blade-stiffened panel is illustrated in Fig. 4. Between the stiffeners the skin undergoes local buckling with a half wavelength approximately equal to the stiffener spacing.

Figure 4. Postbuckling deformations of blade-stiffened Panel

COMPRESSION AND SHEAR TESTS

Two specially designed test rigs were developed for testing the panels under edgewise compression and shear. In each case, load was applied by placing the rigs in a 500 kN servo-hydraulic axial testing machine. In the compression rig, load was applied to the panel by two end fittings bolted to the panel short edges. The long edges were supported by edge members which were guided in the end fittings. These edge members were lightly clamped to the panel long edges. The holes in the panel long edges were drilled 1.5 mm oversize to permit compressive deformation of the panel. The shear rig consisted of four members tightly bolted to the panel edges and pin jointed to permit in-plane shear deformation, see Fig. 5. The responses of the postbuckling panels were monitored using shadow moiré interferometry to assess the out-of-plane deformations and electrical resistance strain gauges placed back-to-back on the top and bottom surfaces.

Figure 5. Test rigs

A number of panels were subjected to low velocity impacts, producing barely visible impact damage (BVID). This was defined as impact damage which was visible to the naked eye at less than two metres. The damage was induced by clamping the edges of the panels to a steel frame and impacting using a drop weight impactor with a tip diameter of 25 mm. It was found that much more energy was required to produce BVID in the postbuckling panel designs. The sandwich panels were subjected to a central impact of 3.5 J. The postbuckling designs were subjected to a central impact of 50 J over the middle stiffener and a 12 J impact in the adjacent skin, midway between the stiffeners.

TEST RESULTS

Of the eight sandwich and blade-stiffened panels, four were tested in compression and four in shear. Two 'I'-stiffened panels were tested in shear and two in compression. Half of the panels were tested with BVID. A summary of the test results is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Test results

	Sandwich		Blade-stiffened		"I"-stiffened	
Compression - 200 N/mm						
Crosshead displacement (mm)	2.3	(2.1)	3.7	(3.8)	3.6*	(3.6*)
Out-of-plane displacement (mm)	2.4	(2.4)	19.1	(18.7)	17*	(17*)
Buckling Load (N/mm)	-	-	81	(81)	90	(90)
Failure load (N/mm)	291	(284)	291	(237)	189	(181)
Specific Strength (kN/kg)	90	(83)	95	(78)	55	(55)
Shear - 200 N/mm						
Crosshead displacement (mm)	6.1	(6.5)	7.0	(5.6*)	9.8	(6.9*)
Buckling Load (N/mm)	-	-	88	(100)	85	(85)
Failure load (N/mm)	306	(231)	242	(165)	229	(173)
Specific Strength (kN/kg)	120	(98)	127	(84)	106	(81)

() Results for panels with BVID

* design ultimate load not achieved. Maximum test value quoted.

The displacements in Table 2 are for the design ultimate loads. Since ultimate failure of the panels was sudden and catastrophic, it was not possible to determine the exact location of the failure initiation. It was also not possible to assess the primary failure mechanism, since in most cases there was significant fibre breakage and delamination present.

The sandwich panels in compression all failed at the ply drops near the core close-out parallel to the short edge. In shear the sandwich panels failed through the centre with a compression failure along the vertical diagonal and a tension failure along the horizontal diagonal. Typical compression failures of the blade-stiffened panel are shown in Fig. 7. The undamaged panels did not fail through the centre of the panel, whereas those with BVID failed in a straight line directly through the central damaged region. The "I"-stiffened panels in compression all failed in the ends at the stiffener run-outs. In shear the postbuckling panels all failed through the middle of the panels with tension and compression failures along each diagonal.

Figure 7. Compression failures of blade-stiffened panels with and without BVID

The reduction in strength of the panels containing BVID is summarised in Table 3. The small reduction in compressive strength for the sandwich and "I"-stiffened panels is probably due to the location of the failures being away from the impact sites. In shear, all designs showed a significant decrease in residual strength.

Table 3. Reduction in static strength due to BVID

Panel Type	Compression	Shear
Sandwich	2%	24%
Blade-stiffened	18%	32%
"I"-stiffened	4%	24%

The results of the FE analysis are generally in good agreement with the experimental results. In particular, the postbuckling behaviour is well predicted. The shadow moiré fringe pattern for the blade-stiffened panel in compression is compared with the out-of-plane displacement contours from the FE analysis in Fig. 8. Similar results for the shear case are shown in Fig. 9.

Figure 8. Test and FE buckling modes for the blade-stiffened panel at 80 kN compression

Figure 9. Test and FE buckling modes for the blade-stiffened panel at 180 kN shear

Tables 1 and 2 indicate a discrepancy between the panel deflections in the FE analysis and in the tests. For the compression case this can be attributed to differences between the ideal edge restraints used in the FE analysis and the test configuration which involved friction and bolt hole interactions. A large discrepancy was also observed between the predicted in-plane displacement of the panels in shear and the actual crosshead displacement of the testing machine. This is probably caused by a small movement or slippage of the panel in the clamped edges of the shear test rig, since only a small change in angle between the frame and the panel edges is required to produce a relatively large additional displacement.

Table 4 compares the first ply failure (FPF) of the FE analysis with two points in the tests. One is the load at which loud cracking was observed and the other is the ultimate load. The initial ply failure load could be expected to correspond to the load at which loud cracking was observed in the tests. This is only true for the blade-stiffened panel in shear. In all other cases the onset of cracking occurred well below the initial ply failure load as predicted by the analysis. In some cases the test ultimate strength actually exceeds the predicted initial ply failure load.

Table 4. Strength prediction vs. test results (N/mm)

Result	sandwich		blade		I	
	comp.	shear	comp.	shear	comp.	shear
FE analysis - FPF	452	270	286	171	200	200
Test - loud cracking	178	305	216	183	167	154
Test - ultimate load	291	305	291	241	189	229

CONCLUSIONS

Two postbuckling composite panel designs have been tested in edgewise compression and shear and compared to a conventional composite sandwich panel. The postbuckling behaviour was accurately predicted using geometric nonlinear finite element methods. In particular, the observed buckle modes were in good agreement with those predicted by the analysis. The panel strengths, however, were not well predicted using the maximum strain, first ply failure criteria. Additional effects such as interlamina shear and through thickness normal stresses are probably significant and need to be considered. There was also significant scatter in the results from the small sample of test panels and a larger number would be required to more accurately assess the strength characteristics. The postbuckling behaviour was found to be very sensitive to the panel edge conditions which need to be adequately represented in any finite element modelling. Ideal edge restraints cannot be assumed for the design of postbuckling structures.

Significant reductions in the residual strength of panels containing BVID were observed for both the sandwich and the postbuckling designs, although much higher impact energies were required to produce BVID in the postbuckling panels. Where only small reductions occurred, the failures were dominated by local details such as stiffener run-outs or core close-outs.

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